

PROPERTIES OF STRONGLY PRE-OPEN SETS IN IDEAL NANO TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

N. SEKAR, R. ASOKAN AND I. RAJASEKARAN,*

ABSTRACT. Aim of this article, Rajasekaran [11] introduced strongly pre- I -open sets and in nano topological spaces. The relationships of strongly pre- nI -open sets with various other nano \mathcal{R}_I -set and nano I -locally closed sets are investigated.

1. INTRODUCTION

An ideal I [13] on a space (X, τ) is a non-empty collection of subsets of X which satisfies the following conditions.

- (1) $A \in I$ and $B \subset A$ imply $B \in I$ and
- (2) $A \in I$ and $B \in I$ imply $A \cup B \in I$.

Given a space (X, τ) with an ideal I on X if $\wp(X)$ is the set of all subsets of X , a set operator $(.)^* : \wp(X) \rightarrow \wp(X)$, called a local function of A with respect to τ and I is defined as follows: for $A \subset X$, $A^*(I, \tau) = \{x \in X : U \cap A \notin I \text{ for every } U \in \tau(x)\}$ where $\tau(x) = \{U \in \tau : x \in U\}$ [1]. The closure operator defined by $cl^*(A) = A \cup A^*(I, \tau)$ [12] is a Kuratowski closure operator which generates a topology $\tau^*(I, \tau)$ called the \star -topology which is finer than τ . We will simply write A^* for $A^*(I, \tau)$ and τ^* for $\tau^*(I, \tau)$. If I is an ideal on X , then (X, τ, I) is called an ideal topological space or an ideal space.

Rajasekaran et.al [8] introduced pre- nI -open sets and α - nI -open sets in the concept of ideal nano topological spaces.

In this paper, Rajasekaran [11] introduced strongly pre- I -open sets and in nano topological spaces. The relationships of strongly pre- nI -open sets with various other nano \mathcal{R}_I -set and nano I -locally closed sets are investigated.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. [7] Let U be a non-empty finite set of objects called the universe and R be an equivalence relation on U named as the indiscernibility relation. Elements belonging to

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*Corresponding author.

the same equivalence class are said to be indiscernible with one another. The pair (U, R) is said to be the approximation space. Let $X \subseteq U$.

- (1) The lower approximation of X with respect to R is the set of all objects, which can be for certain classified as X with respect to R and it is denoted by $L_R(X)$. That is, $L_R(X) = \bigcup_{x \in U} \{R(x) : R(x) \subseteq X\}$, where $R(x)$ denotes the equivalence class determined by x .
- (2) The upper approximation of X with respect to R is the set of all objects, which can be possibly classified as X with respect to R and it is denoted by $U_R(X)$. That is, $U_R(X) = \bigcup_{x \in U} \{R(x) : R(x) \cap X \neq \phi\}$.
- (3) The boundary region of X with respect to R is the set of all objects, which can be classified neither as X nor as not - X with respect to R and it is denoted by $B_R(X)$. That is, $B_R(X) = U_R(X) - L_R(X)$.

Definition 2.2. [2] Let U be the universe, R be an equivalence relation on U and $\tau_R(X) = \{U, \phi, L_R(X), U_R(X), B_R(X)\}$ where $X \subseteq U$. Then $R(X)$ satisfies the following axioms:

- (1) U and $\phi \in \tau_R(X)$,
- (2) The union of the elements of any sub collection of $\tau_R(X)$ is in $\tau_R(X)$,
- (3) The intersection of the elements of any finite subcollection of $\tau_R(X)$ is in $\tau_R(X)$.

Thus $\tau_R(X)$ is a topology on U called the nano topology with respect to X and $(U, \tau_R(X))$ is called the nano topological space. The elements of $\tau_R(X)$ are called nano-open sets (briefly n-open sets). The complement of a n -open set is called n -closed.

In the rest of the paper, we denote a nano topological space by (U, \mathcal{N}) , where $\mathcal{N} = \tau_R(X)$. The nano-interior and nano-closure of a subset O of U are denoted by $I_n(O)$ and $C_n(O)$, respectively.

A nano topological space (U, \mathcal{N}) with an ideal I on U is called [4] an ideal nano topological space and is denoted by (U, \mathcal{N}, I) . $G_n(x) = \{G_n \mid x \in G_n, G_n \in \mathcal{N}\}$, denotes [4] the family of nano open sets containing x .

In future an ideal nano topological spaces (U, \mathcal{N}, I) is referred as a space.

Definition 2.3. [4] Let (U, \mathcal{N}, I) be a space with an ideal I on U . Let $(\cdot)_n^*$ be a set operator from $\wp(U)$ to $\wp(U)$ ($\wp(U)$ is the set of all subsets of U).

For a subset $O \subseteq U$, $O_n^*(I, \mathcal{N}) = \{x \in U : G_n \cap O \notin I, \text{ for every } G_n \in G_n(x)\}$ is called the nano local function (briefly, n-local function) of A with respect to I and \mathcal{N} . We will simply write O_n^* for $O_n^*(I, \mathcal{N})$.

Theorem 2.1. [4] Let (U, \mathcal{N}, I) be a space and O and B be subsets of U . Then

- (1) $O \subseteq B \Rightarrow O_n^* \subseteq B_n^*$
- (2) $O_n^* = C_n(O_n^*) \subseteq C_n(O)$ (O_n^* is a n -closed subset of $C_n(O)$),
- (3) $(O_n^*)_n^* \subseteq O_n^*$,
- (4) $(O \cup B)_n^* = O_n^* \cup B_n^*$,
- (5) $V \in \mathcal{N} \Rightarrow V \cap O_n^* = V \cap (V \cap O)_n^* \subseteq (V \cap O)_n^*$,
- (6) $J \in I \Rightarrow (O \cup J)_n^* = O_n^* = (O - J)_n^*$.

Theorem 2.2. [4] Let (U, \mathcal{N}, I) be a space with an ideal I and $O \subseteq O_n^*$, then $O_n^* = C_n(O_n^*) = C_n(O)$.

Definition 2.4. [6] A subset A of a space (U, \mathcal{N}, I) is $n\star$ -dense in itself (resp. $n\star$ -perfect and $n\star$ -closed) if $O \subseteq O_n^*$ (resp. $O = O_n^*$, $O_n^* \subseteq O$).

The complement of a $n\star$ -closed set is said to be $n\star$ -open.

Definition 2.5. [3] A subset O of U in a nano topological space (U, \mathcal{N}) is called nano-codense (briefly n -codense) if $U - O$ is n -dense.

Theorem 2.3. [4] Let (U, \mathcal{N}, I) be an ideal nano space. Then \mathcal{I} is n -codense if and only if $O \subseteq O^*$ for every n -open set O .

Definition 2.6. [4] Let (U, \mathcal{N}, I) be a space. The set operator C_n^* called a nano \star -closure is defined by $C_n^*(O) = O \cup O_n^*$ for $O \subseteq U$.

It can be easily observed that $C_n^*(O) \subseteq C_n(O)$.

Theorem 2.4. [5] In a space (U, \mathcal{N}, I) , if O and B are subsets of U , then the following results are true for the set operator $n\text{-cl}^*$.

- (1) $O \subseteq C_n^*(O)$,
- (2) $C_n^*(\phi) = \phi$ and $C_n^*(U) = U$,
- (3) If $O \subset B$, then $C_n^*(O) \subseteq C_n^*(B)$,
- (4) $C_n^*(O) \cup C_n^*(B) = C_n^*(O \cup B)$.
- (5) $C_n^*(C_n^*(O)) = C_n^*(O)$.

Definition 2.7. A subset O of a space (U, \mathcal{N}) , is called a

- (1) nano α - I -open (resp. α - nI -open) [8] if $O \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))$.
- (2) nano pre- I -open (resp. pre- nI -open) [8] if $O \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(O))$.
- (3) nano t_α - I -set (resp. t_α - nI -set) [10] if $I_n(O) = I_n(C_n^*(O))$.
- (4) nano \mathcal{R}_α - I -set (resp. \mathcal{R}_α - nI -set) [10] if $O = S \cap K$, where S is n -open and K is t_α - nI -set.
- (5) nano δ - I -open (resp. δ - nI -open) [9] if $I_n(C_n^*(O)) \subseteq C_n^*(I_n(O))$.
- (6) nano \mathcal{R}_I -set (or) nano \mathcal{O}_I -set (resp. $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set) [11] if $O = S \cap K$ where S is n -open and K is $(I_n(K))_n^*$.
- (7) nano I -locally closed (resp. nI -locally closed) [11] if $O = S \cap K$ where S is n -open and K is $n\star$ -perfect.

Note : The largest pre- nI -open (α - nI -open) set contained in O , denoted by $p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$ ($\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$), is called the pre- nI -interior (α - nI -interior).

3. PROPERTIES OF STRONGLY PRE-OPEN SETS IN IDEAL NANO SPACES

Definition 3.1. A subset O of an ideal nano space (U, \mathcal{N}, I) , is called a strongly nano pre- I -open (resp. SP - nI -set) [11] if O is pre- nI -open and \mathcal{R}_α - nI -set

Example 3.1. Let $U = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $U/R = \{\{a\}, \{d\}, \{b, c\}\}$ and $X = \{a, c\}$. Then $\mathcal{N} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, U\}$. Let the ideal be $I = \{\phi, \{c\}\}$.

Theorem 3.2. If O is any subset of an ideal nano space, then the next conditions are holds.

- (1) $p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = O \cap I_n(C_n^*(O))$.
- (2) $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))$.

Proof.

- (1) Since $O \cap I_n(C_n^*(O)) \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(O))$

$$= I_n(I_n(C_n^*(O)))$$

$$= I_n(C_n^*(O) \cap I_n(C_n^*(O)))$$

$$\subseteq I_n(C_n^*(O \cap I_n(C_n^*(O))))$$

$O \cap I_n(C_n^*(O))$ is a pre- nI -open set contained in O and so $O \cap I_n(C_n^*(O)) \subseteq p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$.

Since $p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$ is pre- nI -open, $p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O))) \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(O))$ and so $p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \subseteq O \cap I_n(C_n^*(O))$.

Hence $p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = O \cap I_n(C_n^*(O))$.

$$\begin{aligned} (2) \text{ Since } O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O))) &\subseteq I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O))) = I_n(I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))) \\ &= I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O) \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))) \\ &\subseteq I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O) \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))) \\ &= I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O))))), \end{aligned}$$

$O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))$ is an α - nI -open set contained in O and so

$$O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O))) \subseteq \alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O).$$

Since $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$ is α - nI -open,

$$\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(I_n(\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)))) \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))$$

and so $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \subseteq O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))$.

Hence $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O)))$. □

Theorem 3.3. *If O is a \mathcal{R}_α - nI -set of an ideal nano space, then $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = I_n(O)$.*

Proof.

Forever, $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \supseteq I_n(O)$. Since O is a \mathcal{R}_α - nI -set, $O = S \cap K$ where S is n -open and $I_n(C_n^*(I_n(K))) = I_n(K)$. Now

$$O \subseteq K \text{ implies } I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O))) \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(I_n(K))) = I_n(K).$$

Therefore, by Theorem 3.2(1), $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O))) \subseteq O \cap I_n(K) = S \cap I_n(K) = I_n(S \cap K) = I_n(O)$. Therefore, $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \subseteq I_n(O)$, and so $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = I_n(O)$. □

Theorem 3.4. *If O is a δ - nI -open set of an ideal nano space, then $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$.*

Proof.

Since every α - nI -open set is a pre- nI -open set,

$$\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \subseteq p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O). \text{ By Theorem 3.2(1), } \alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = O \cap I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O))).$$

Since O is δ - nI -open, $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \supseteq O \cap I_n(I_n(C_n^*(O))) = O \cap I_n(C_n^*(O)) = p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$ and so $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) \supseteq p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$. Therefore, $\alpha\mathfrak{J}I_n(O) = p\mathfrak{J}I_n(O)$. □

Theorem 3.5. *If (U, \mathcal{N}, I) is any ideal nano space, then the following conditions are holds.*

- (1) *If O is $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set, then O is a semi- nI -open.*
- (2) *If O is semi- nI -open set, then O is a δ - nI -open.*

Proof.

(1) If O is $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set, then $O = S \cap K$ where S is n -open and $K = (I_n(K))_n^*$. Therefore, $O = S \cap K = S \cap (I_n(K))_n^* \subseteq (S \cap I_n(K))_n^* = (I_n(S \cap K))_n^* = (I_n(O))_n^* \subseteq C_n^*(I_n(O))$ and so O is semi- nI -open.

(2) If O is semi- nI -open, then $O \subseteq C_n^*(I_n(O))$. Now $I_n(C_n^*(O)) \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(C_n^*(I_n(O)))) = I_n(C_n^*(I_n(O))) \subseteq C_n^*(I_n(O)) \implies O$ is a δ - nI -open set. □

Remark. *If an ideal nano space,*

- (1) *pre- nI -open set and $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set.*
- (2) *every n -open set is \mathcal{SP} - nI -set.*

(3) every \mathcal{R}_α - nI -set is pre- nI -open.

Example 3.6. The Example 3.1,

- (1) the set $\{a, d\}$ is $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set but not pre- nI -open
- (2) the set $\{c\}$ is \mathcal{SP} - nI -set is not n -open.
- (3) the set $\{b\}$ is pre- nI -open but not \mathcal{R}_α - nI -set.

Remark. If an ideal nano space,

- (1) pre- nI -open sets and \mathcal{R}_α - nI -sets are independent.
- (2) pre- nI -open sets and δ - nI -open sets are independent.

Example 3.7. The Example 3.1,

- (1) the set $\{b\}$ is pre- nI -open but not \mathcal{R}_α - nI -set.
- (2) the set $\{d\}$ is \mathcal{R}_α - nI -set but not pre- nI -open.
- (3) the set $\{c\}$ is δ - nI -open but not nI -open.
- (4) the set $\{b\}$ is pre- nI -open but not δ - nI -open.

Theorem 3.8. If (U, \mathcal{N}, I) is any ideal nano space and $O \subseteq U$, then the following conditions are equivalent.

- (1) O is n -open.
- (2) O is both \mathcal{SP} - nI -open and δ - nI -open.

Proof.

(1) \implies (2) is clear.

(2) \implies (1) Suppose O is \mathcal{SP} - nI -open and also a δ - nI -open set. By Theorem 3.4, since O is pre- nI -open, $\alpha\mathcal{I}I_n(O) = p\mathcal{I}I_n(O) = O$. By Theorem 3.3, $\alpha\mathcal{I}I_n(O) = I_n(O)$. Therefore, $O = I_n(O) \implies O$ is n -open. □

Theorem 3.9. If (U, \mathcal{N}, I) is any ideal nano space where I is n -codense and $O \subseteq U$, then the following conditions are equivalent.

- (1) O is n -open.
- (2) O is α - nI -open and nI -locally closed set.
- (3) O is pre- nI -open and nI -locally closed set.
- (4) O is pre- nI -open set and $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set.
- (5) O is \mathcal{SP} - nI -open and $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set.
- (6) O is \mathcal{SP} - nI -open and semi- nI -open set.
- (7) O is \mathcal{SP} - nI -open and δ - nI -open set.

Proof.

(1) \implies (2) If O is n -open, then O is α - nI -open. Since I is n -codense, by Theorem 2.3, $O \subseteq O_n^*$, and so $O = O \cap O_n^*$. Therefore, O is nI -locally closed.

(2) \implies (3) Follows from the fact that every α - nI -open set is pre- nI -open.

(3) \implies (4) If O is nI -locally closed, then $O = S \cap O_n^*$ for some n -open set S . Since $O \subseteq O_n^*$, by Theorem 2.2, $O_n^* = C_n^*(O)$. Since O is pre- nI -open, $O \subseteq I_n(C_n^*(O)) = I_n(O_n^*)$ and so $O_n^* \subseteq I_n(O_n^*) \subseteq (O_n^*)_n^* \subseteq O_n^*$. Therefore, $O_n^* = I_n(O_n^*)_n^*$ which implies that O is an $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set.

(4) \implies (5) If A is an $n\mathcal{R}_I$ -set, then $O = S \cap K$ where S is n -open and $K = (I_n(K))_n^*$. Now $I_n(C_n^*(I_n(K))) = I_n(I_n(K) \cup (I_n(K))_n^*) = I_n(I_n(K) \cup K) = I_n(K)$. It follows that O is \mathcal{SP} - nI -open.

(5) \implies (6) Follows from Theorem 3.5(1).

(6) \implies (7) Follows from Theorem 3.5(2).

(7) \implies (1) Follows from Theorem 3.8. □

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Kuratowski, *Topology*, Vol I. Academic Press (New York) 1966.
- [2] M. Lellis Thivagar and Carmel Richard, *On nano forms of weakly open sets*, International Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Invention, 1(1)(2013), 31-37.
- [3] O. Nethaji, R. Asokan and I. Rajasekaran, *New generalized classes of an ideal nano topological spaces*, Bull. Int. Math. Virtual Inst., 9(3)(2019), 543-552.
- [4] M. Parimala, T. Noiri and S. Jafari, *New types of nano topological spaces via nano ideals* (to appear).
- [5] M. Parimala and S. Jafari, *On some new notions in nano ideal topological spaces*, International Balkan Journal of Mathematics (IBJM), 1(3)(2018), 85-92.
- [6] M. Parimala, S. Jafari and S. Murali, *Nano ideal generalized closed sets in nano ideal topological spaces*, Annales Univ. Sci. Budapest., 60(2017), 3-11.
- [7] Z. Pawlak, *Rough sets*, International journal of computer and Information Sciences, 11(5)(1982), 341-356.
- [8] I. Rajasekaran and O. Nethaji, *Simple forms of nano open sets in an ideal nano topological spaces*, Journal of New Theory, 24(2018), 35-43.
- [9] N. Sekar, R. Asokan and I. Rajasekaran, *On δ -open sets in ideal nano topological spaces*, communicated.
- [10] I. Rajasekaran, O. Nethaji and R. Prem Kumar, *Perceptions of several sets in an ideal nano topological spaces*, Journal of New Theory, 23(2018), 78-84.
- [11] I. Rajasekaran, *Weak forms of strongly nano open sets in ideal nano topological spaces*, Asia Matematika, 5(2)(2021), 96-102.
- [12] R. Vaidyanathaswamy, *The localization theory in set topology*, Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., 20(1945), 51-61.
- [13] R. Vaidyanathaswamy, *Set topology*, Chelsea Publishing Company, New York, 1946.

N. SEKAR

RESEARCH SCHOLAR, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS,, MADURAI KAMARAJ UNIVERSITY, MADURAI, TAMIL NADU, INDIA.

Email address: sekar.skrss@gmail.com

R. ASOKAN

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICS, MADURAI KAMARAJ UNIVERSITY, MADURAI, TAMIL NADU, INDIA.

Email address: rasoka_mku@yahoo.co.in.

I. RAJASEKARAN

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, TIRUNELVELI DAKSHINA MARA NADAR SANGAM COLLEGE, T. KALLIKULAM-627 113, TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

Email address: sekarmelakkal@gmail.com.